

A TYPOLOGY OF CHRONIC DEFENSIVE AUTONOMIC STATES AS SPECIFIC ANTECEDENTS TO DISEASE ETIOLOGY

A WHITE PAPER

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ABSTRACT

Correlating stress-related diseases with their specific autonomic antecedents provides 1) a novel and clinically-relevant taxonomy of stress-related disease etiology, 2) an empirical basis for early preventive intervention if there is detection or monitoring of enduring pathogenic autonomic states, and 3) pathways to more effective treatment of underlying autonomic strata beneath symptoms.

For the past decade, Hearth Science has been developing a new foundation model of autonomic physiology, and correlating pathogenic autonomic states with stress-related disease etiology. In this white paper we map out general findings, exploring the autonomic undergirding of a variety of illustrative disease pathologies, as well as characterizing some of the complex non-linear interactions between autonomic substrates, the immune system, and the neuroendocrine system. This mapping provides a framework for understanding autonomic antecedents to common stress-related pathology ranging from post-traumatic stress injuries, to pain syndromes, to gastro-intestinal disease, auto-immune disease, and beyond. It focuses not on symptoms in target organs, but rather on the autonomic pattern language of the down-regulation of specific physiological systems as a result of chronic or archived allostatic loads in the body, which are differentiated by neurology and neurochemistry.

INTRODUCTION

The question of disease etiology – what causes illbeing – is a principal organizing question for all medical and healing arts systems.^[1] The advent of germ theory in Europe in the mid-19th century, which states that microorganisms cause specific diseases by invading a host, displaced older theories such as the miasma theory and notions of spontaneous generation. This revolutionized allopathic medicine by providing an empirical basis for understanding, preventing, and treating infectious disease, leading to vaccines, antibiotics, improved sanitation, and a profound shift in medical praxis (e.g., surgeons washed their hands before performing surgery!). While still referred to as a *theory*, germ theory undergirds modern medical praxis at a foundational level.

60-80% of what brings modern people into primary care is stress-related.

All stress-related illness is autonomic, resulting from fundamental alterations to the resting baseline state of the Autonomic Nervous System (ANS), the neurobiological sequelae thereto, and their attendant entanglements with other physiological systems.^[2] Yet there is no generally-accepted allopathic theory or framework that unites the taxonomy of stress-related disease with a cogent understanding of the autonomic antecedents that lead to these disease typologies.

Rather, allopathic medicine, which emerged from a mind-body split and tends to view the body as a complex metabolic machine, and the mind as either an epiphenomenon of brain chemistry (psychiatry) or the instantiated psychology of self

1 Whether the system is ayurveda, or traditional chinese medicine, or an indigenous shamanic healing tradition, this question of ‘what are the causes of illbeing’ is the fundamental question to which the development of a healing system is the response.

2 Complex chronic illness, for example, arises at the interface between autonomic, immune, and endocrine systems.

(psychology/ counseling), conceptualizes issues of the body (medical) and issues of the mind (mental health) as being of fundamentally different characters, and therefore categorically mis-diagnoses stress-related disorders at scale, since all stress related disorders have both body (physical) and mind (mental health) components.

This structural failure to accurately conceptualize stress-related disorders leads to 1) healthcare systems needlessly incinerating astounding pileage of coin on invasive, ineffective, and partial treatment [ineffective resource use for the healthcare systems] 2) causing needless suffering to patients and clients with stress-related disorders, who are typically shuffled between primary care physicians, organ-specific specialists (gastro-enterology, cardiology, nephrology, neurology, etc.), and psychiatry or counseling.

Since none of these practitioners has a diagnostic axis that permits the totality of a stress-related condition to come into view, treatment is recursively partial. E.g., the gastro-enterologist treats the inflammatory response in the gut, but has no cure for anxiety. The psychiatrist has a prescription for anxiety but it doesn't help with gut inflammation. Neither treatment address brain fog or chronic fatigue, and in fact might make those worse, et cetera. Patients mired in this system feel neither seen nor understood, nor are they effectively treated [ineffective treatment for patients]. Those who can afford it therefore assemble their own retinues of out-of-network practitioners who are paid out of pocket, seeking out functional and integrative medical doctors whose purview at least extends across the mind-body divide yet is unlikely to comprehensively address the ANS since much of functional medicine, while informed by systems biology and a general orientation towards stress reduction, is generally more focused on nutrition, infection, inflammation, and genetics.

When autonomic physiology is centralized as the primary diagnostic and treatment axis for stress-related disorders, it

restructures the diagnostic taxonomy of much of the illbeing of the modern world, and reconciles the split between physical and mental health symptoms that siloes stress-related disorders that are in fact always mindbody issues into diagnostically incomplete fragments.

For the past decade, Hearth Science has been developing a new foundation model of autonomic physiology, and correlating pathogenic autonomic states with stress-related disease etiology. This mapping provides a framework for understanding autonomic antecedents to common stress-related pathophysiology, focused not primarily on symptoms in target organs, but rather on the autonomic pattern language of the down-regulation of specific physiological systems as a result of chronic or archived allostatic loads in the body, which are differentiated by neurology and neurochemistry.

We believe that a medicine that centralizes autonomic physiology in the diagnosis and treatment of stress-related disorders is capable of vastly improving the quality of life for modern humans and effectively treating a range of conditions that allopathic medicine erroneously asserts are incurable.

AN AUTONOMIC MANDALA

Reviews of the literature suggest that 60–80% of what brings people into primary care settings is stress-related. Stress is a (if not *the*) fundamental substrate of illbeing. Stress is a concept that everyone thinks that they understand, but whose technical composition as a quantifiable term of medical art breaks down immediately under serious scrutiny. There is good stress (eustress) and there is bad stress, which is the kind people generally refer to when they are talking about stress. But some stress, related to the fight–fight responses [hot stress], which is the kind of stress most people are talking about when they talk or think about stress, elevates the heart-rate, increases arousal,

focuses the eye gaze, prepares the body to mobilize, and tightens the muscles. While other modes of stress [cold stress] decrease the heart-rate, inhibit the breathing, defocus the eyes, immobilize the body, and decrease muscle tone. This second variant of stress, comprised of hypo, rather than hyper-arousal, correlates etiologically with the development of chronic illness and a host of other pathophysiologies, yet is recognized neither by traditional neurology nor by most mainstream allopathic medical systems, because its underlying autonomic neurology is the activation of a differentiated parasympathetic autonomic system of which allopathic medicine does not yet recognize the existence [Dorsal Vagal System originating in DMX of the medulla oblongata in Polyvagal Theory, Grounding System in Autonomics].

For the past decade, Health Science has been developing a novel *in vivo* neurophysiological cartography of the Autonomic Nervous System (ANS) and its affiliated neurochemistries that redraws the functional architecture and inter-relationships between the three primary autonomic systems, significantly updating their embodied neural cartography beyond what is commonly understood in both traditional neurology and Polyvagal Theory (Porges, 1994). Utilizing a range of qualitative and quantitative methodologies, including phenomenological and interoceptive investigation, the investigation of trans-cultural indigenous child-rearing practices, evolutionary comparative neuro-anatomy, *in vivo* autonomic neurological tracking, and novel autonomic measurement technologies that centralize respiration as the physiological portal to the ANS, we have delineated novel autonomic architectures and their entrainment/ decoordination across a range of neuroceptive scenarios (safety, danger, and lifethreat). Analysis of the 13 most common integrals of neuroception, autonomic neurology, and affiliated neurochemistry prevalent in a sample of 2,742 individuals interacting with our clinical software has yielded a mapping of the autonomic states that a general population seems to spend the most time in. We refer to this mapping of autonomic states as an Autonomic Mandala.

BIOLOGICAL AXIOM OF THE EFFICIENT USE OF ENERGY

A principal hallmark of biology is the efficient use of energy. Biological systems must deliberately prioritize how metabolic resources are deployed moment-to-moment to optimize the conditions for organismic survival and wellbeing.

Unlike modern humans and nation states, which can survive while accumulating formidable financial debt, biological systems cannot accumulate metabolic debt without paying a very serious price for it. Caloric bankruptcy in the Living World results in death.

Disturb a songbird in the middle of a winter night who has fluffed its feathers to create an envelope of warmth around itself (this is the original down jacket), and it will be dead

by morning. Once disturbed it does not have enough metabolic reserves to recreate the heat envelope without caloric intake, and a songbird is not able to feed at night to restore its reserves. Biology has slender margins of metabolic reserve, generally speaking. (Songbirds don't have refrigerators.)

AUTONOMIC STATES AS ENERGY-PROCESSING TEMPLATES

We conceptualize an autonomic state as an energy-processing template for experience. The ANS, which is tasked with 1) governing the internal milieu and 2) up and down-regulating survival and restoration responses, dynamically tunes the body-mind to optimize the efficient deployment of energy relative to the *perceived* inner and outer environments in which we find ourselves.

From the perspective of the ANS, and its role in survival function, the most salient globalized variable with respect to any present moment circumstance is whether we find the body-mind to be

- Safe enough to become socially available
- In Danger
- or Under Lifethreat

Stephen W. Porges, PhD, the Developer of Polyvagal Theory (1994) has coined the term 'neuroception' to refer to this differentiating embodied autonomic detection of safety, danger, and lifethreat, which in turn governs the surfacing of the energy processing templates through which our experience flows.

Maximizing for the efficient use of energy, the survival functions of the Autonomic Nervous System that govern the up and down-regulation of sensory, visceral, and attentional systems *severely alter the energy deployed to non-essential*

biological systems when the body perceives itself to be in danger or lifethreat. This is why chronic and non-resolving stress is antecedent to so many categories of illbeing.

An organism will, based on this moment-to-moment neuroceptive detection, exhibit a globalized cluster of autonomic tunings of sensory, visceral, and attentional systems to respond to relevant perceived survival pressures from the inner or outer environment. When the body detects danger or lifethreat, it unhesitatingly and often brutally down-regulates non-essential biological functions. What does this mean practically?

From the standpoint of survival, many biological functions are luxurious, including the following

- digestion
- immune function
- aspects of memory
- concentration
- sleep
- restoration functions generally
- social availability
- sexual function

If the body detects danger or lifethreat, it down-regulates these systems until the body is no longer detecting danger or lifethreat.

Stress responses, evolutionarily, are designed for rapid onset and rapid resolution. The human lineage is ecologically adapted to respond to acute physical and environmental stressors. Our lineage history evolved in the context of small band hunter gatherer bands, and a feature of our deep evolutionary history is also that the presence of these bands was crucial to the subsequent downshifting of threat responses once the danger had passed. Our ancestors in deep time regularly endured extreme physical stresses, but experienced almost no social stress.

Modern humans, by contrast, find ourselves in an inverted context. Modernity is characterized by extreme loneliness, isolation, and disconnection.^[3]

Absent the small band to help us co-regulate (human wellbeing and neurobiological regulation is social in nature), modern humans are uniquely susceptible to threat responses becoming chronic and non-resolving. In direct contrast to our lineage history, modern humans often have little physical stress, yet endure extreme social stress. These conditions directly subvert the body's ability to return to baseline in the wake of shifting into defensive stress responses.^[4]

This deficient social context creates a secondary problem for the biology. We live in a world of existential threats (as humans always have), yet the relational context that historically helped us downshift these threats once they had passed has been denatured. Therefore modern humans do not typically recover well from shifting into danger and lifethreat responses. Stress

3 See the Cigna Loneliness Study – Loneliness in America, 2025, from which the graphic above is drawn.

<https://newsroom.thecignagroup.com/loneliness-in-america>

See the Surgeon General's Advisory: Our Epidemic of Loneliness and Isolation: The U.S. Surgeon General's Advisory on the Healing Effects of Social Connection and Community

<https://www.hhs.gov/sites/default/files/surgeon-general-social-connection-advisory.pdf>

4 This is why our work is focused largely on activating the autonomic drivers of connection. See *The Neurobiology of Connection: Rewilding the Deep Nervous System for Wellbeing*, Natureza Gabriel, Jaguar Imprints, 2024.

responses that become chronic and non-resolving leave the body biologically compromised.

AUTONOMIC STATES AS PATTERN LANGUAGE

The body, based on present moment perceived neural detection of safety, danger, or lifethreat, dynamically surfaces autonomic states that govern the visceral control of organs and tune our senses and attention in predictable ways. Autonomic state governs six facets of experience, five of which are simple: our visceral state, emotional range, cognitive frame, interpretation of the world around us, and behaviors. The sixth facet relates to our sense of identity and is more complexly constructed over time, as people tend to identify with the states they spend the most time in- e.g., someone whose physiology has trouble exiting a flight state, for whom this becomes a neurophysiological baseline, will identify as 'an anxious person'.

Autonomic states have individual variation, but represent a clinically-useful pattern language with respect to presentation, affect, affiliated cognitions, etc. They can arise with varying degrees of intensity. A person in a flight state that is mild can experience this as a vague sense of worry, while someone experiencing the state more intensely may experience it as a sense of pervading fearfulness or anxiety, while someone experiencing it acutely describes it as terror. As a state intensifies, the autonomic neurological center of gravity of the state becomes more pronounced, and the flow of affiliated neurochemistry becomes more intense. This translates into more severe visceral modulation of organ systems (both up- and down-regulation depending on the system) and the recruitment of relevant extero-senses.

Again using the example of the continuum of a flight response: when the response is mild, a person's visual system may be

mildly recruited to attempt to identify a source of threat, but this recruitment may stay beneath the threshold of conscious awareness. The person may have a vague sense that they are looking for something. By the time the state reaches an intensity where the person is actively anxious, the eyes have been consciously recruited by the ANS, and the person is actively looking for threats (scanning for exits, seeking to identify signals of danger in the faces of people around them, their body language, etc.). With someone in terror, the only thing the eyes are looking for is the source of threat, until the body shifts into shutdown and begins to immobilize.

PERCEIVED THREAT

I have been mindful to note, in the preceding sections, that the biology is optimizing for efficient energy deployment relative to the *perceived* inner and outer environment. Our neuroceptions of safety, danger, and lifethreat are accrued based on our subjective life experience: there is no absolute standard for this.

The mechanism whereby the biology perceives threat (calibrates might be a better word here since this detection is often beneath the threshold of conscious awareness) is based on neuroceptive setpoints in the ANS that are tuned by previous life experience.

In utero and early life experiences of stress, including stress hormones conveyed to the fetus from the mother, birth stress, the social stress experienced by the mother, the degree to which the mother and other primary caregivers are available, attuned, and regulated, the degree to which attachment is secure, the degree to which the infant's needs are met, the degree to which children experience nestedness in the ancestral baseline of the evolved nest (1. welcoming social climate, 2. soothing perinatal experiences, 3. multiple bonded nurturers, 4. responsive relationships, 5. positive moving touch, 6. child-directed breastfeeding, 7. self-directed social play, 8. nature immersion

and connection, 9. regular healing practices)(Narvaez, 2014)¹⁵¹ are neurobiological variables that govern autonomic setpoints that arrange our implicit autonomic bodily experience of safety, danger, and lifethreat.

These experiential and chemical inputs sculpt the baseline parameters of autonomic physiology, predisposing us to experience an inner and outer world that either feels predictable, stable, and safe, or not.

This is important because the determination of whether something is safe, dangerous, or life threatening to an individual nervous system is referenced within the nervous system. For this reason, an event can be inviting to one person and overwhelming to another (public speaking, for example). An event can be exhilarating to one person and terrifying to

5 See the research of Darcia Narvaez, PhD, on the Evolved Nest (Evolved Developmental Niche). "Every animal has a nest for its young that matches up with the maturational schedule of the offspring (Gottlieb, 1997)." Humans do as well. "The Evolved Nest (or Evolved Developmental Niche; EDN) refers to the nest for young children that humans inherit from their ancestors. It's one of our adaptations, meaning that it helped our ancestors survive. Most characteristics of the evolved nest emerged with social mammals more than 30 million years ago. Humans are distinctive in that babies are born highly immature (only 25% of adult-sized brain at full-term birth) and should be in the womb another 18 months to even resemble newborns of other species! As a result, the brain/body of a child is highly influenced by early life experience. Multiple epigenetic effects occur in the first months and years based on the timing and type of early experience. Humanity's evolved nest was first identified by Melvin Konner (2005) as the "hunter-gatherer childhood model" and includes breastfeeding 2-5 years, nearly constant touch, responsiveness to baby's needs, multiple responsive adult caregivers, free play with multiple-aged playmates, positive social support for mom and baby. Calling these components the Evolved Developmental Niche, Narvaez and colleagues add to the list soothing perinatal experience (before, during, after birth), a positive, welcoming social climate, Nature immersion and connection, and regular healing practices. All these are characteristic of the type of environment in which the human genus lived for 99% of its existence."

<https://sites.nd.edu/darcianarvaez/the-evolved-nest-evolved-developmental-niche-edn/>

another (skydiving for example). For this reason, modalities that work clinically in the domain of trauma healing often say that the trauma is in the nervous system not the event. More precisely, the trauma is in the nervous system's interpretation of the event, and connected directly to the specific defensive autonomic neurology and neurochemistry elicited, and subsequently retained (if it does not outflow), by the body.

SALUTOGENIC STATES, PATHOGENIC STATES

The Autonomic Mandala on page 7 presents 13 autonomic states on a clock face with numerical locations (fight 3a/flight 3b at 3 o'clock are two distinct states with identical neuroception, neurology, and overlapping activation chemistry).

Five of the states on the mandala are salutogenic: health-creating. (8 restore, 9 enjoy, 10 connect, 11 play, 12 compete). Six states on the mandala are pathogenic if they become chronic and non-resolving (2 appease, 3a fight, 3b flight, 4 placate, 5 freeze (tonic immobility), 6 shutdown). Two states on the mandala are context-dependent, and can either be salutogenic or pathogenic depending on contextual factors (1 accommodate, 7 union).

What does it mean for a state to be health-creating? All salutogenic autonomic states require that the body experience a sufficient embodied sense of safety to entrain all three autonomic neurological systems into coordination. While danger signals can be constant, safety is pulsatile in nature. These states have different degrees of arousal, mobilization, and degrees of connection chemistry (a restoration state may be experienced in the stillness of meditation, yet a compete state might happen racing around a tennis court), yet all of them entrain and coordinate biological rhythms. Wellness arises spontaneously when we are able to spend more of our present moments in one of these states.

Six states on the mandala are pathogenic *if they become chronic and non-resolving*. This is an important caveat, because there is no such thing as a bad or undesirable autonomic state. Our ability to shift into defensive states when we encounter threats, including our ability to move into profound states of shutdown, permits us to survive experiences that would otherwise be unendurable, and likely to induce the breakdown of a coherent sense of self.

The problem that humans face is not that we shift into defensive states like fighting, fleeing, placating, freezing, and shutting down. The problem is that we cannot shift back out of these states once we have shifted into them.

Peter Levine, PhD, the developer of Somatic Experiencing™, a naturalistic approach to the resolution of trauma, developed the modality partly by marvelling at the capacity of animals in the wild to come out of deep shutdown states they had entered if conditions became safe again. ^[6] He noticed that when this happened, animals often entered into involuntary (autonomically-mediated) neurogenic tremoring. He also noted that animals placed in zoos (confinement) lost the ability to display these innate resilient responses. Modern humans, in this regard, typically resemble animals in confinement. Most of us have no idea how to make our way back from these states.

If we enter pathogenic states enough times, if they become non-resolving, our neuroceptive baselines begin to shift in the direction of the particular defensive responses that we use more often. This represents a form of neuroplastic learning in the autonomic systems. Simply put, if, as a small child I am bitten by a dog, I might be alarmed by this experience but if I am skillfully accompanied back from my high arousal state,

6 You can find videos on Youtube, for example, of gazelles on the savannah coming out of shutdown states after being taken down by a leopard if the leopard gets distracted or is forced to leave.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-OggITik6G4>

am able to get through the pain of it and metabolize my fear chemistry, this may not leave an enduring autonomic impact. If I am not able to clear this chemistry and arousal and return to baseline, the next time I see a dog I am likely to experience arousal. This is a form of autonomic learning. The residual allostastic load in my system tells me that dogs are not safe. This is not a cognition, at least first. It is far beneath thinking. It is a viscerally-apprehended sensation in the body accompanied in all likelihood by a spike in arousal, accelerated heart rate, etc. While the residual allostastic load in my body tells me that dogs are not safe, this may or may not be true. Clearly some dogs are not safe (the one that bit me). Yet the generalization of this experience to all dogs— the change in autonomic setpoint— is a result in my inability to clear the archived neurological and chemical load.

We have a tendency to want to treat a situation like this psychologically, but it is not psychological despite the fact that it has psychological repercussions. It is physiological: the result of an arousal response to being in danger, and its attendant neurological and neurochemical sequelae, and the fact that they have not flowed out of the body. I can talk about this all I want in a therapeutic setting without touching the neurobiological setpoints that govern my bodily response to dogs, which means I will never actually get to the neurological strata driving the response. Alternatively, I can shift the neurobiological setpoints themselves directly through an autonomic intervention without having to say a word (unless part of what did not happen during the bite event was that my autonomic nervous system wanted to vocalize and yet I did not).

Two states on the mandala are highly contextual, and can function either as salutogenic or pathogenic depending on context. In the context of more collectivist cultures, where there is a strong sense of 'WE', accommodating can be a way of adaptively meeting the needs of the group at large, and in this context of the greater group and our affiliation can be salutogenic. In the context of a 'WE' no one likes a person who is

rigid about what they want. Yet in more individualistic cultures, accommodation often leads to appeasing, and is more likely to be pathogenic.

Likewise, the state of union, which is characterized by boundary dissolution without fear (endogenous opioids to dissolve boundaries, enough oxytocin that this happens within the envelope of feeling safe), can be salutogenic in certain contexts (e.g., making love) and pathogenic in other contexts (getting indoctrinated into a cult).

CLASSIFICATION SCHEMA OF AUTONOMIC ANTECEDENTS TO DISEASE

If we are going to build a meaningful schema for understanding the autonomic antecedents to stress-related disorders, we have to make distinctions between disease etiology where the autonomic strata is primary or secondary, and between disease etiology where autonomics are the single driver of a condition, or tangle with other physiological systems.

The simplest classification system that preserves the above distinctions would be the determination of whether the autonomic strata is

- 1) the primary antecedent of the disease (e.g., anxiety)
- 2) a primary antecedent that pairs with a secondary system (e.g., inflammatory bowel disease)
- 3) a primary antecedent that pairs with a secondary and a tertiary system (e.g., auto-immune disease)
- 4) implicated in the disease but not the primary antecedent (e.g., Complex Regional Pain Syndrome)

Please note that the listings that follow are not exhaustive, but illustrative. There are far more disease conditions with autonomic antecedents than we have studied or worked on clinically. What we are addressing below are conditions that are

either within the scope of our clinical or research praxis and therefore where we have some clear sense about the underlying autonomic conditions relate to pathophysiology.

INTRODUCTION OF A NOVEL TERM: AUTONOMIC COMPOSITION

We have coined the term ‘autonomic composition’ to refer to the archived composition of allostatic loads a person carries, as distinct from the present-moment balance of autonomic presentation. As a clinical term, this helps us distinguish between present moment autonomic state in which an individual is presenting, and what the body is carrying as archived neurology and neurochemistry.

For simplicity, consider three primary neuroceptive conditions of safety, danger, and lifethreat. We analogize these to three states of water. Consider then that an adult is like a water droplet with some percentage of their nervous system baselined in safety (liquid water), some in danger responses that have not returned to baseline (steam), and some in lifethreat responses that have not returned to baseline (ice).

We can measure this composition anecdotally through clinical intake when clients share their history/ medical history, quantifiably through measurement of autonomic metrics (respiration, HRV, galvanic skin response, electro-dermal) at intake and at various points along their treatment trajectory, and qualitatively through observation of the way that their nervous systems respond to autonomic intervention.

See illustration pages 28-29.

1) PATHOPHYSIOLOGY WHERE AUTONOMICS

ARE THE PRIMARY ANTECEDENT

Anxiety (antecedent autonomic state: flight) is the embodied experience of a chronic and non-resolving flight response. If this experience is of a short duration, the person might refer to it as episodic anxiety. As it becomes chronic and non-resolving the experience of anxiety becomes more chronic.

Depression (antecedent autonomic state: shutdown) is the embodied experience of a chronic and non-resolving shutdown response. If this experience is of a short duration, the person might refer to it as episodic depression. If it becomes chronic and non-resolving, it might be clinically referred to as major depression. If the person’s center of autonomic gravity shifts out of shutdown, they will experience the depression lifting. If they shift into a connection state (8, 9, 10, 11, or 12) they will experience this as a shift back into wellbeing. If they shift out of it into a danger state (3a, 3b) they might shift into anxiety, or into aggression, or into a form of mania.

Frozen Shoulder (antecedent autonomic state: fight). Typically happens when the body elicits a self-protective fight response but is then constrained from completing the behavior. This is part of a larger category of pathophysiology resultant to the body being unable to complete an autonomically-elicited movement behavior, e.g., **Restless Leg Syndrome**.

Manic Depression (Bipolar Disorder)(autonomic antecedent shutdown/ fight-flight) is chronic and non-resolving alternation between shutdown and danger states.

Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (autonomic antecedent is typically shutdown) is actually an injury, and more sensibly referred to as Post-Traumatic Stress Injury. This is an embodied experience of shutdown caused by a traumatic event. It is important to further distinguish the typology, as simple PTSD is generally caused by a shock trauma, whereas complex PTSD

is often the neurobiological sequelae of developmental trauma and fits into a different place in this schema (e.g., autonomics as primary antecedent entangled with impact on attachment systems).^[7]

Medical Trauma (autonomic antecedents can be shutdown, tonic immobility, fight-or-flight) We would be remiss here if we did not differentiate a category of medical or post-surgical trauma, where the body activates a lifethreat response in response to a medical procedure or surgery. Being confined in an MRI, or undergoing surgery that the body does not welcome can lead to lifethreat responses. If the body endogenously shifts into lifethreat, anaesthesia is not properly metabolized and can be retained in the tissues.^[8]

2) PATHOPHYSIOLOGY WHERE AUTONOMICS PAIR WITH A SECONDARY SYSTEM

Impact Collisions (autonomic antecedents can be shutdown/tonic immobility/fight-or-flight) If a person endures

7 It creates a different set of psychobiological problems to be attacked by a bear in the wild (shock trauma), versus having to live with a bear in the same house (developmental trauma). Shock trauma in our experience is more likely to elicit shutdown responses (*there's a bear, It is overwhelming, I detect lifethreat, my body shuts down*), developmental traumas more likely to elicit appease and placate responses (*there's a bear, it is overwhelming, I detect lifethreat, it is living in my house, I need it not to attack me*). Appease and placate states invite immunological entanglement (social availability to something that is trying to harm us), thus adding a third physiological system to the mix.

8 In our clinical work we have helped clients clear anaesthesia from surgeries that happened in excess of fifty years prior.

an accident where there is impact and a loss of balance with vectors of force (fall, skiing accident, car accident), there is an autonomic component to this that pairs with disturbances to the vestibular/proprioceptive system in the movement trajectory of the accident. As arousal rises prior to impact, in tandem with vectors of force acting upon balance mechanisms in the body (vestibular, proprioceptive) the autonomic nervous system tangles with the vestibular and proprioceptive systems.

Inflammatory Bowel Disease (autonomic antecedent can be shutdown/ fight-or-flight) If the body shifts into an enduring danger or lifethreat response, digestion is down-regulated because from the point of view of the ANS it is a non-essential function for survival. This down-regulation by definition impairs peristaltic rhythm.

If chronic danger or lifethreat endures long enough there is a predictable sequence of sequelae, including de-oxygenation of the digestive tract, which changes its pH, which changes its microbiome, which creates a climate inhospitable to beneficial bacteria and preferential to the overgrowth of bacteria we do not want. This predictably leads to a decrease in the bacteria that synthesize vitamins and strengthen immunity. In tandem, bacteria, yeast, and other microorganisms we do not want proliferate, their metabolic byproducts cause toxicity, this leads to epithelial cell gapping in the walls of the intestine, this gapping leads to the passage of molecules into the bloodstream that should not be there.

When this happens, the immune system must get involved. Since 80% of the immune cells in the human body are localized in the gut, and since immunological activity is accompanied by the release of inflammatory cytokines, we now have a situation with an autonomic antecedent that is coupled with activation of the immune system in the gut.

3) PATHOPHYSIOLOGY WHERE AUTONOMICS ENTANGLE WITH MULTIPLE SYSTEMS

Complex Chronic illness (autonomic antecedents can be shutdown, tonic immobility, placate, or appease) Non-linear entanglement of autonomic, immune, and endocrine systems. Often begins with chronicity of a placate or appease response, characterized by a person being open to something that is trying to harm us, typically a person. These tend to be primary relationships with caregivers early in life. This may or may not lead directly to symptomology.

Early progression to involvement of digestion, and immune system activation. Immuno-reactivity can increase, leading to food allergies, sensitivities, etc. Often endocrine involvement. Inciting incident can be an infection (Lyme Disease), mold toxicity, or other environmental factors, stress, or other various causative agents. Characterized by complex non-linear interaction of autonomic, immune, and endocrine responses typically leading to globalized Cell Danger Responses (Naviaux, 2008)^[9] that decrease the body's sensitivity to signals of safety originating in the Central Nervous System.

There are a variety of pathophysiologies that cluster together under this category, including **Myalgic Encephalomyelitis/Chronic Fatigue Syndrome (ME/CFS)**, and **Mast Cell Activation Syndrome (MCAS)**.

Various auto-immune disorders (autonomic antecedents can be placate or appease) Disease pathways here tend to arise from autonomic antecedents where a person has learned to be open (available) to something that is trying to harm them. Pathways here can resemble those of Inflammatory Bowel Disease (e.g., immune involvement due to digestive disturbance resultant to down-regulation of the guts), but tend to implicate

9 [Metabolic Features of the Cell Danger Response.](#)

endocrine/ hormonal systems as well.

4) PATHOPHYSIOLOGY WHERE AUTONOMICS IMPLICATED BUT NOT THE PRIMARY ANTECEDENT

Because allostatic loads accumulate unless they are cleared, by the time most people are adults, they have significant archived stress in the body.

ARCHIVED ALLOSTATIC LOADS AS PRE-EXISTING CONDITIONS

The Adverse Childhood Experiences Study (Felitti and Anda, 1998) demonstrated that exposure to early childhood adversity adversely impacts nearly all physical and mental health domains later in life. The study revealed a graded dose-response relationship between early adversity (ACES), and the development of pathophysiology in study participants fifty years later.^[10]

What the study did not attempt to do was to differentiate the specific autonomic responses of any given study participant to the particular adverse experiences they endured.

Imagine for a moment that it was possible to observe the specific autonomic responses of each child in the study at each moment when an adverse experience was happening (this could be accomplished with a neurofeedback device measuring respiration or HRV). As a child endures each of these events, the defensive pattern language of the autonomic nervous system mobilizing resources to defend would be observable to us. We would be able to see whether a child appeased, fought, fled,

10 Average age of study participants (17,421 patients of Kaiser Permanente in San Diego) was 57 years old. They were reporting on events from early childhood, fifty or more years prior)

placated, shifted into tonic immobility or shut down. With this data, we would be able to correlate disease etiology later in life to these earlier autonomic antecedents, particularly to the extent that they did not resolve.

For some study participants who had frequent early exposures, likely resulting in both intense danger responses (fight-and-flight mobilization) and deep shutdown experiences (immobilization) we might see diverse pathophysiology develop. But for other participants, we might begin to be able to see clear correlation between the particular defensive strategies that became chronic and non-resolving and the particular disease that develops. In both cases, you can probably recognize that by the time a child with four or more ACES exposures reaches adulthood, they are carrying around a significant archived allostatic load. Functionally, this load is a pre-existing condition.

It is

- reducing vitality
- interfering with the regulation of organ systems
- inhibiting healthy entrainment of autonomic systems
- modifying baseline parameters of autonomic function
- likely engendering self-medicating or coping strategies, hopefully not maladaptive (e.g., addiction)

If there is an insult later in life— an infection for example— this pre-existing autonomic condition, which is not directly causal to the illness, will still play a profound role in how it unfolds. Be the insult an illness, an injury, or some other assault to the body or mind, the prior archived allostatic load is at play in how the body responds.

Complex Regional Pain Syndrome (pre-existing autonomic conditions) is an idiopathic condition characterized by pain greater than would be expected by an injury. While the cause of the syndrome is typically the injury itself, the condition develops as a result of pre-existing archived autonomic loads.

Parkinson's Disease (pre-existing baseline of early childhood shutdown) When early shutdown experiences are anatomically localized in the spine, endogenous opioid (enkephalin) blockade of ascending sensory signals in dorsal root ganglia deprives midbrain dopaminergic systems of inputs. Over long spans of time this can lead to degredation of the midbrain dopaminergic systems that control goal-directed motor movement. Early childhood shutdown localized in the spinal dorsal root ganglia is the pre-existing condition that later leads to the development of Parkinson's disease.

CONCLUSION

When autonomic physiology becomes the primary axis of diagnosis and treatment for stress-related disorders, it focalizes different features of the pathophysiology, and allows us to discern the ways in which chronicity/ non-resolution/ archiving of specific autonomic states and their affiliated allostatic loads are antecedent to particular classes of disease.

This approach reconciles the fracturing of disease etiology into physical and mental health components common to traditional allopathic medicine and contemporary mainstream mental health treatments (psychiatry/counseling). It provides insight into the origin of many conditions that allopathic medicine considers idiopathic, and permits novel diagnostic and intervention possibilities that target the root strata from which pathophysiology emerges.

While this paper provides an illustrative taxonomy of differentiated autonomic antecedents to a variety of pathophysiologies, a complete taxonomy re-organizes the cartography of our understanding of the roots of illbeing, and provides actionable diagnostic and treatment pathways that will diminish human suffering and improve quality of life for the statistically significant percentages of the human population suffering from stress-related disorders and sub-optimal wellbeing.

**AUTONOMICS NEUROANATOMY:
CONNECTION SYSTEM IN BLUE,
MOVEMENT SYSTEM IN YELLOW,
GROUNDING SYSTEM IN RED**

**AUTONOMICS META-MODEL OF IN VIVO ANS FUNCTIONING
RECONCILING COOPERATIVE COORDINATION WITH JACKSONIAN DISSOLUTION**

IF NEUROCEPTION = SUFFICIENT SAFETY, AUTONOMIC SYSTEMS COORDINATE AND ARE SALUTOGENIC
 IF NEUROCEPTION = DANGER, AUTONOMIC SYSTEMS DE-COORDINATE (JACKSONIAN DISSOLUTION)
 IF NEUROCEPTION = LIFETHREAT, AUTONOMIC SYSTEMS FURTHER DE-COORDINATE
 ERGO: THE ONLY TIME WHEN THERE IS A SINGLE AUTONOMIC SYSTEM AVAILABLE IS SHUTDOWN
 UNDER CONDITIONS OF LIFETHREAT

NEUROCEPTION

AUTONOMIC SYSTEMS RECRUITED

PLAY

COMPETE

ACCOMMODATE

ENJOY

CONNECTION

RESTORE

UNION

SHUTDOWN

APPEASE

FIGHT / FLIGHT

FIGHT/FLIGHT

FREEZE

PLACATE

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